

Appendix 1: Description of residential water demand methods.

Factors	Variables	Parameters	Models	Methods/Approaches	Location/spatial scale	References
Socio-demographic factors	Population	Time (t); initial time (t ₀); population growth rate (r); initial population P(t ₀); population at time t P(t); and N: population growth threshold.	$P(t) = \frac{P(t_0)e^{r(t-t_0)}}{1 + \frac{P(t_0)(e^{r(t-t_0)} - 1)}{N}}$	Logistic regressions/ SSP	China/ pearl River Basin	Chen et al 2022
		Not provided	Not provided	Linear regression/Unit consumption ratio method	China / Huaihe River Basin	Wang et al 2018
		Not provided	Not provided	Dynamic system / SSP scenarios	China	Jiang et al 2023
		Not provided	Not provided	Hybrid ANN model (artificial neural networks), several regression models and a system dynamics/SSP model	Alberta (Canada)/ Edmonton area	Liu, 2020
		Not provided	Not provided	Dynamic system	China / city of Urumqi	Chang et al 2015
		Not provided	Not provided	Conceptual framework	France and Spain / Herault basin (France) and Ebro basin (Spain)	Grouillet et al 2015
		Not provided	Not provided	Multiple linear regression / equation Alternative scenarios	USA/ Los Angeles	Ashoori et al 2017
		P _t = Population at a given time in the future; P ₀ = Current population T = projection period K = constant	$P_t = P_0 + K_t$	Alternative scenarios	Malaysia/ Selangor	Nur Iffika Ruslan et al 2022
		Not provided	Not provided	A Monte Carlo simulation approach Climate scenarios (A1, A2 and B1)	Australia/ Blue Mountains, New South Wales	Haque et al 2014
		Not provided	Not provided	Framework using regression/SSP	(1/8° spatial resolution) / global scale	Parkinson et al 2016
		Where P(t) is the population at time t and P(t-dt) is the population at time t-dt. BR, DR, IR and ER represent the birth rate, death rate, immigration rate and emigration rate respectively.	$P(t) = 2 \times P(t - dt) * (BR - DR + IR - ER)$	Dynamic system Increase wastewater treatment rate by 50%; reduce irrigation water demand per hectare by 20%; and increase total	China/Bayingolin Prefecture	Guangyang Wu et al 2013

				water supply by 5%.		
		TP is the total population; IP is the augmented population, and GRP is the population growth rate.	$TP(t) = TP(t - dt) + IP \times dt$ $IP = TP \times GRP$	systems dynamics, orthogonal design and copula analysis(IA-SOC)	China/Jing-Jin-Ji region	Yanpeng Cai et al 2018/China/Jing-Jin-Ji region
		Not provided	Not provided	Scenario-based approach	Okanagan Basin (British Columbia): Town of Oliver, Town of Penticton and City of Kelowna	Neale et al., 2007
Urbanization rate		Where δ is the urbanization rate; C is the integral constant; and d is the parameter to be determined. Suppose t_0 is the base year; and U_0 is the base year urban population and R_0 is the base year rural population.	$\delta = \frac{1}{1 + Ce^{-dt}}$ <p style="text-align: center;">And</p> $c = \frac{R_0}{U_0}$	Logistic regressions/ SSP projection	China/ pearl River Basin	Chen et al 2022
		Where Y is an urban expansion index, y_1 (Urbanization level): Ratio of non-agricultural population to total population. y_2 (Industrial structure): Ratio of tertiary industry output to GDP. y_3 (Living standard): GDP per capita. y_4 (Environment): Green area per capita.	$Y = \log (y_1.y_2.y_3.y_4)$	Dynamic scenario system SSP	China / city of Urumqi	Chang et al 2015
		Not provided	Not provided	Dynamic scenario system SSP	China	Jiang et al 2023
		Not provided	Not provided	Framework using regression/ Climate scenarios SSP	(1/8° spatial resolution) / global scale	Parkinson et al 2016
Water demand per capita		CI is the climate impact factor (i.e. the impact of decreasing precipitation and increasing temperature, in percentage terms, on water demand and supply), WUP_{pc} is the projected water use per capita.	$WD_{PC} = WUP_{PC} \times (1 + CI)$	Dynamic system	Australia / South East Queensland	Sahin et al 2014

	<p>i represents residential water end-uses, lf represents low-flow appliances including toilets, showers, washing machines, BAT, etc. with high efficiency and low flow, gw represents grey water reuse and treatment, $f_{lf,i}$ are the percentages of households equipped with low-flow appliances, $r_{lf,i}$ are the fractional reductions in residential water demand (dimensionless), $R_{gw,i}$ is the reduction in water consumption resulting from the graywater treatment policy (L/inhabitant/day), and $R_{xr,i}$ is the reduction in water consumption resulting from the landscaping policy (L/inhabitant/day).</p>	$PCWD = \sum_i \{ \{ (f_{lf,i}(1 - r_{lf,i}) + (1 - r_{lf,i})) \} * BPCWD_i - R_{gw,i} - R_{xr,i} \}$	End-use method		Liu, 2020
	<p>PCD is per capita demand in liters per day. S and W are seasonal and weather variables. UER is the trend unemployment rate in the Portland MSA and I and LT are the indicator and long-term trend variables, respectively. α; β; γ; θ; η; and ω are the unknown coefficients to be estimated and u is the error term with Gaussian properties.</p>	$PCD = \alpha + \beta S + \gamma W + \theta I + \eta UER + \omega LT + u$	Time series structural regression model	Portland (USA) / city of portland	Parandvash and Chang, 2016
	<p>RP and UP represent the rural and urban populations respectively, and RDWDPC and UDWDPC represent the per capita water demand of the rural and urban populations respectively, in liters per capita per day.</p>	$TDWD = RP * RDWDPC * 365/10^3/10^8 + UP * UDWDPC * 365/10^3/10^8$	Dynamic system/ Increase wastewater treatment rate by 50%; reduce irrigation water demand per hectare by 20%; and Increase water consumption per hectare.	China/Bayingolin Prefecture	Guangyang Wu et al 2013
	<p>RPWQ is the rural population water quota, RP is the rural population, UPWQ is the urban population water quota, UP is the urban population, TP is the total population, UR is the urbanization rate.</p>	$DW = RPDW + UPDW$ $RPDW = RPWQ \times RP$ $UPDW = UPWQ \times UP$ $UP = TP \times UR$	Approche intégrée de la dynamique des systèmes, du plan orthogonal et de l'analyse des copules (IA-SOC) systems dynamics, orthogonal design and copula analysis(IA-SOC)	China/Jing-Jin-Ji region	Yanpeng Cai et al 2019

Economic factors	Water-saving consciousness	<p>y_{ijt} is the daily water consumption of household i in county j on calendar date t; $f(\mathbf{temp}_{jt})$ is a series of temperature intervals for recovering the non-linear relationship between average daily temperature and water consumption; (γ) associated coefficients interpreted as an increase in water consumption for an additional day in the specific temperature interval; \mathbf{X}_{jt} is a vector of selected daily weather parameters (which may influence water consumption) up to quadratic terms, including total precipitation, relative humidity, wind speed, sunshine hours and atmospheric pressure; $(\delta_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{year}_t)$ fixed effects per dwelling year; ϵ_{ijt} is an idiosyncratic shock to water use, grouped at the dwelling level.</p>	$y_{ijt} = \alpha + f(\mathbf{temp}_{jt})\gamma + \delta_{jt} \cdot \mathbf{year}_t + \theta_t + \epsilon_{ijt}$	Panel fixed-effects regression/ IPCC-SSP	China/ 10 provinces	Ping Qin et al 2022
		<p>$W_{mun,i}$ is the average monthly water demand for month i [m3/cap/d]; $T_{mon,i}$ is the average monthly temperature for month i; a, b and c are regression coefficients [-]; and MW_{mun} is the long-term average value of municipal water demand [m3/cap/d] when $T_{mon,i} < 0^\circ\text{C}$.</p>	$W_{mun,i} = \begin{cases} MW_{mun} \cdot T_{mon,i}^a & T_{mon,i} \geq 0 \\ MW_{mun} \cdot T_{mon,i}^b & T_{mon,i} < 0 \end{cases}$	Dynamic systems	Canada/ Province of Saskatchewan	Lina Wu et al 2020
		<p>Median household income (I), household size (i.e. number of people per house) (Hs) and maximum monthly temperature (T).</p>	$\ln q = 3,11 + 0,25 \log(I) + 0,57 \log(Hs) + 0,24 \log(T)$	Regressions / Future population and explanatory variable projections were based on a set of assumptions	City of Riyadh, Saudi Arabia	Al-Mutaz et al 2011
	Water-saving consciousness	<p>Where K is water-saving awareness, θ is the annual growth rate of water-saving awareness and M is the upper limit of water-saving awareness.</p>	$K = Ae^{-\left(\frac{\theta}{M}\right)t}$	Projection SSP/ Dynamic system	China/ pearl River Basin	Chen et al 2022
		Not provided	Not provided	Multiple linear regression equation/ Alternative scenarios	USA/ Los Angeles	Ashoori et al 2017
	Water pr...	<p>IWS_t is the increase in water supply for domestic water demand in year t;</p>	$\begin{cases} WP_t = WP_{t-1}f_1, ITWD_{t-1} > IWS_{t-1} \\ WP_t = WP_{t-1}f_2, ITWD_{t-1} > IWS_{t-1} \end{cases}$	SSP projection	China/ pearl River Basin	Chen et al 2022

		ITWD _t is the increase in total domestic water demand in year t; WP _t is the water price in year t. f1 is the increase in water price when supply is less than demand, and f2 is the ratio of reduction in water price when supply is greater than demand.					
		Not provided	Not provided	Business as usual. IPCC AR4 under emission scenarios A1B; Scenario combinations	China / Beijing megalopolis	Qin et al 2018	
		Not provided	Not provided	Multiple linear regression equation Alternative scenarios	USA/ Los Angeles	Ashoori et al 2017	
		Not provided	Not provided	A Monte Carlo/ simulation approach Climate scenarios (A1, A2 and B1)	Australia/ Blue Mountains, New South Wales	Haque et al 2014	
	Urban population income	UPI _t are the per capita disposable incomes of urban residents in year t; UPI _{t0} are the per capita disposable incomes of urban residents in base year t ₀ ; k ₂ is the growth rate of per capita urban disposable incomes.	$UPI_t = UPI_{t_0} + k_2(t - t_0)$	Linear regression/ SSP projection	China/ pearl River Basin	Chen et al 2022	
		Not provided	Not provided	Business as usual; IPCC AR4 under emission scenarios A1B; Scenario combinations	China / Beijing megalopolis	Qin et al 2018	
	Climatic factors	Precipitation	P _t are daily precipitation and Pdl (0) _t represent their contemporaneous deviations from the conditional means.	$P_t = \hat{\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \hat{\beta}_i S_i + \sum_{j=1}^6 \hat{\gamma}_j S_j + e_t$ $Pdl(0)_t = P_t - \left(\hat{\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \hat{\beta}_i S_i + \sum_{j=1}^6 \hat{\gamma}_j S_j \right)$	Time series structural regression model/ CMIP5-RCP	Portland (USA) / city of portland	Parandvash & Chang 2016
			Not provided	Not provided	Multiple linear regression equation/ Alternative scenarios	USA/ Los Angeles	Ashoori et al 2017
			Not provided	Not provided	A Monte Carlo/ simulation approach Climate scenarios (A1,	Australia/ Blue Mountains, New South Wales	Haque et al 2014

	Temperature	Not provided	Not provided	A2 and B1) Linear regression / Unit consumption ratio method / Projection: RCP	China / Huaihe River Basin	Wang et al., 2017
		T_t are daily temperature and $Tdl(0)_t$ represent their contemporaneous deviations from the conditional means	$T_t = \hat{\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \hat{\beta}_i S_i + \sum_{j=1}^6 \hat{\gamma}_j S_j C_j + \hat{\delta} P_0 + \hat{\lambda} P_{-1} + \varepsilon_t$ $Tdl(0)_t = T_t - \left(\hat{\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^6 \hat{\beta}_i S_i + \sum_{j=1}^6 \hat{\gamma}_j S_j C_j + \hat{\delta} p_0 + \hat{\lambda} P_{-1} \right)$	Time series structural regression model /CMIP5-RCP	Portland (USA) / city of portland	Parandvash & Chang, 2016
		Not provided	Not provided	Multiple linear regression equation/ Alternative scenarios	USA/ Los Angeles	Ashoori et al 2017
		Not provided	Not provided	A Monte Carlo/ simulation approach Climate scenarios (A1, A2 and B1)	Australia/ Blue Mountains, New South Wales	Haque et al 2014
		Not provided	Not provided	Linear regression / Unit consumption ratio method / Projection: RCP	China / Huaihe River Basin	Wang et al., 2017
		Not provided	Not provided	Framework using regression/ RCP climate scenarios	(1/8° spatial resolution) / global scale	Parkinson et al 2016
	Climate change and water use	Not provided	Not provided	Scenario-based approach	Okanagan Basin (British Columbia): Town of Oliver, Town of Penticton and City of Kelowna	Neale et al., 2007
Physical properties of the medium	Housing type	Not provided	Not provided	Scenario-based approach	Okanagan Basin (British Columbia): Town of Oliver, Town of Penticton and City of Kelowna	Neale et al., 2007

Appendix 2: Calculation methods for water demand in the residential sector.

Variables	Parameters	Models	Methods/ Approaches	Location/spatial scale	References
Municipal water demand	POP _{area} is the population living in rural, urban or city areas (respectively, r, t and u), PCC _{area} is the per capita water consumption in each area.	$W^{mun} = \sum_{area \in r, t, u} POP_{area} * PCC_{area}$	Scenario-based approaches	Red River Basin, Vietnam	Mauri et al.,2022
	LW ^t is domestic water demand (10 ⁴ m ³); urban water demand LuW ^t ; rural water demand LrW ^t ; rural population Pr ^t (10 ⁴ p); per capita water consumption in the rural area, LQr ^t (l/p.d).	$LW^t = LuW^t + LrW^t + Pu^t \times LQu^t \times 365/1000 + Pr^t \times LQr^t \times 365/1000$	Linear regression /Unit consumption ratio method	China / Huaihe River Basin	Wang et al 2017
	Temperature (T); Precipitation (P)	WP = f (Population, T, P, n, n-1, n-2, n-3)	Multiple regression model	City of Skopje/ Macedonia	Donevska et al., 2019
	Y represents i observations of subsequent development-related demand at the geographic coordinate (u _i , v _i), x _{ik} is the set of k explanatory variables (i.e. education, median age, NDVI, temperature, form index and developed land per capita;) at a given location i (i.e. census tracts) and ε is an error term. B and α are coefficients determined garce a Kernel function	$y_i = \alpha(u_i, v_i) + \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_k(u_i, v_i)x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i$	Geographically weighted regression	North Carolina and South Carolina/ USA	Sanchez et al.,2020
	Population (POP); municipal water intensity for the base year (i _{mun,t0}), slope (s _{mun,cat}), and multiplier 0.365 is applied for unit conversion.	$M = POP \times (i_{mun,t0} + s_{mun,cat} \times (t - t_0)) \times 0,365$	Equation from model H08	Global approach	Wada et al., 2016

	DWD is domestic water demand, POP is national population and DWUI is domestic water use intensity. $DWUI_{cnt,t}$ is domestic water withdrawal per capita in 2000	$DWD_{cnt,y} = POP_{cnt,y} \times EDev_{cnt,y} \times TDev_{cnt,y} \times DWUI_{cnt,t0}$	Equation from PCR-GLOBWB model		
Residential Water Demand	ICP: income per capita	$RESWAT = 0.03 * Population + 0.3 * PCI - 0.00$	Linear regression model	City of Addis Ababa/ Ethiopia	Kitessa et al.,2021
	The f function f_{tot} is defined by three parameters: the minimum demand (m_{tot}), the maximum additional demand (M_{tot}) and the curve parameter (γ_{tot}); GDP represents average GDP per capita. The parameter m_{tot} is set to correspond to basic needs: m The other two parameters of f_{tot} must be estimated statistically at country level, using data on GDP, population and domestic water demand.	$Q_{tot} = f_{tot}(GDP) = m_{tot} + M_{tot} [1 - \exp(-\gamma_{tot} \cdot GDP^2)]$	Economic demand functions to 2060	Mediterranean region	Neverre et al.,2015
	The rate of increase in domestic water demand ϕ_{dwd} is a function of the population growth rate (ϕ_{pop}) and income (GDP per capita, ϕ_{gdpc}),	$\phi_{dwd} = \phi_{pop} + \eta \cdot \phi_{gdpc}$	Regression based on historical data	Global scale	Cai et al,(2002)

		Number of animals to be watered (Ni) Livestock (B) -Small livestock (b) Water quota for livestock (Q _B , Q _b) Livestock water quota (i) (Quota) _i	$DEel_{(t)} = \sum_{i=1}^n Quota_i \times Ni_{(t)}$	CLD,SD	China	Xie and Ringler (2023), Qin et al (2018), Qin et al (2012),
			$DEel = DE_B + DE_b$ $DE_B = B \times Q_B$ $DE_b = b \times Q_b$	SD, orthogonal plane and copula analysis (IA-SOC)	China	Cai (2018),
		Water demand Aquaculture (DE) ^{aq} Surface evaporation loss (PEc) Infiltration loss (IL) Precipitation (P) Aquaculture area(S) ^{aq}	$FROM^{aq} = EP_c + PI-P$	GCM, GCAM CPR	Vietnam	Mauri et al (2022)
			$DE^{aq} = S^{aq} + Q$	SD, orthogonal plane and copula analysis (IA-SOC)	China	Cai (2018),
	Forest	Forest water demand (DEF) Forest area(S _r); Forest area growth (CS _r) Growth rate (r)	$DEF = Sf \times Q$ $CSf = Sf \times r$ $Sf(t) = Sf(t - dt) + CSf \times dt$	SD, orthogonal plane and copula analysis (IA-SOC)	China	Cai (2018),
Climatic factors	Precipitation	Average precipitation (P) _m Effective precipitation (P) _{eff}	$\Delta P_{ij} = (P_{m, fut, ij} - P_{m, base, ij})$	AOGCM, LARS- WG CPR	Iran	Mehrazar et al (2020); Jafari et al (2021),
				GFDL CM3, MIROC5, MRI- CGCM3, RCP	Canada	AGÉCO Group (2019),
			$P_{eff} = \frac{P_m(125-0,2 \times P_m)}{125} \text{ si } P_m \leq 250mm$ $P_{eff} = 125 + 0,1 \times P_m \text{ si } P > 250mm$	IWRAM= CanESM2+SDSM+Q TM+LSTM CPR	China	Dang et al (2024),
			$P_{eff} = \frac{P \times (125 - 0,6 \times P)}{125} \text{ si } P \leq \frac{250}{3} mm$ $P_{eff} = \frac{125}{3} + 0,1 \times P \text{ si } P > \frac{250}{3} mm$	MCM, CPR	France , Spain 8 × 8 km	Grouillet et al.(2015),
			$P_{eff} = P \times \frac{4,17 - 0,2 \times P}{4,17} \text{ si } P < 8,34mm. day^{-1}$ $P_{eff} = 4,17 + 0,1 \times P \text{ si } P \geq 8,34mm. day^{-1}$	CPR	United States,	Yang et al.(2019),
	Temperature	Average temperature (T _m) Minimum and maximum temperature (x x) _{min, max}	$\Delta T_{ij} = (T_{m, fut, ij} - T_{m, base, ij})$	AOGCM//LARS- WG CPR	Iran	Jafari et al (2021), Mehrazar et al (2020);
			$x' = \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}}$		Canada	Liu (2020),

Appendix 4: Variables relating to water demand in the industrial, commercial, and institutional sectors.

Factors	Variables	Parameters	Models	Methods/Approaches	Location/spatial scale	References
Socio-demographic factors	Gross domestic product	Not provided	Not provided	Regressions Business as usual; IPCC AR4 under emission scenarios A1B; Scenario combinations	China / Beijing megalopolis	Qin et al 2018
	Revenue	Not provided	Not provided	Regressions Business as usual; IPCC AR4 under emission scenarios A1B; Scenario combinations	China / Beijing megalopolis	Qin et al 2018
Economic factors	Industrial water prices	Not provided	Not provided	Regressions Business as usual; IPCC AR4 under emission scenarios A1B; Scenario combinations	China / Beijing megalopolis	Qin et al 2018
Physical properties of the medium	Environmental protection	Y_t is a vector of $K \times 1$ endogenous variables, p is the shift order, u is a vector of constant terms, A_1, \dots, A_p are $K \times K$ parameter matrices, and ε_t represents a vector of $K \times 1$ random error columns.	$Y_t = U + A_1 \cdot Y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p \cdot Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t$ ($t = 1, 2, \dots, T$)	vector autoregression model	China / Jiangsu Province	Wang et al 2019
Technological factors	Improving water use technology	Not provided	Not provided	Regressions Business as usual; IPCC AR4 under emission scenarios A1B; Scenario combinations	China / Beijing megalopolis	Qin et al 2018
	Technological progress	Y_t is a vector of $K \times 1$ endogenous variables, p is the shift order, u is a vector of constant terms, A_1, \dots, A_p are $K \times K$ parameter matrices, and ε_t represents a vector of $K \times 1$ random error columns.	$Y_t = U + A_1 \cdot Y_{t-1} + \dots + A_p \cdot Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t$ ($t = 1, 2, \dots, T$)	vector autoregression model	China / Jiangsu Province	Wang et al 2019
	Industrial water demand	WDIP is water demand for industrial product in 10^4 RMB and GIP is gross industrial product in 10^8 RMB, both in cubic meters.	$TIWD = WDIP * GIP * 10^4 / 10^8$	Dynamic system Increase wastewater treatment rate by 50%; reduce irrigation water demand per hectare by 20%; and increase total water supply by 5%.	China/Bayingolin Prefecture	Wu et al 2013

	<p>IW is industrial water demand, IAV is industrial value added, and IAVWQ is water quota per 10⁴ of industrial value added. IIAV is the increase in industrial value added, RIAV is the growth rate of industrial value added, t is the current time and dt is the duration.</p>	$IW = IAV \times IAVWQ$ $IAV(t) = IAV(t - dt) + IIAV \times dt$ $IIAV = RIAV \times IAV$	<p>Approche intégrée de la dynamique des systèmes, du plan orthogonal et de l'analyse des copules (IA-SOC) in english systems dynamics, orthogonal design and copula analysis(IA-SOC)</p>	<p>China/Jing-Jin-Ji region</p>	<p>Cai et al 2018</p>
	<p>Not provided</p>	<p>Not provided</p>	<p>CEEMD-ARIMA combination CEEMD: Collective Empirical Modal Decomposition WaterGAP2 global water use model equation SSP-RCP scenarios</p>	<p>China/ Henan Province</p>	<p>Zang et al 2022</p>
	<p>GDP =GDP of the city ICP: income per capita</p>	$INDWAT = 0.05 * GDP + 0.2 * PCI + 0.02$	<p>Linear regression model</p>	<p>City of Addis Ababa/ Ethiopia</p>	<p>Kitessa et al.,2021</p>
	<p>Electricity generation (ELC); base year(t_0); industrial water intensity ($S_{ind,t0}$) at t_0, and slope, or annual rate of improvement in water intensity ($s_{ind,cat}$).</p>	$I = ELC \times (i_{ind,t0} + S_{ind,cat} \times (t - t_0))$	<p>Equation from model H08</p>	<p>Global scale</p>	<p>Wada et al., 2016</p>
	<p>IWD is industrial water demand, $EDev_{cnt,t}$ is economic development, and $TDev_{cnt,t}$ is technological development. GDP, EL, EN and HC are respectively gross domestic product, electricity production, energy consumption and household consumption. pc and cnt are per capita and per country. t and t_0 represent respectively the year and the reference year.</p>	$IWD_{cnt,t} = EDev_{cnt,t} \times TDev_{cnt,t} \times IWD_{cnt,t0}$ $EDev_{cnt,t} = average \left(\left(\frac{GDP_{pc,t}}{GDP_{pc,t0}} \right)^{0.5}, \left(\frac{EL_{pc,t}}{EL_{pc,t0}} \right)^{0.5}, \left(\frac{EN_{pc,t}}{EN_{pc,t0}} \right)^{0.5}, \left(\frac{HC_{pc,t}}{HC_{pc,t0}} \right)^{0.5} \right)$	<p>Equation from PCR-GLOBWB model</p>		
	<p>Gross domestic production per capita (GDPC); time variable (T); α is the intercept; β is the income coefficient, reflecting the evolution of the intensity of</p>	$IWDI = \alpha + \beta \cdot GDPC + \gamma \cdot T$	<p>Regression based on historical data</p>	<p>Global scale</p>	<p>Cai et al (2002)</p>

		industrial water use as a function of GDPC; and γ is the time coefficient.				
Water demand from manufacturing industry	I_{MAN} intensity of water use in manufacturing industry; IVA industrial value added. GDPca is the annual GDP per capita, RHL is the production ratio between heavy and light industry. b_0 , b_1 and b_2 are constants specific to the Pearl River delta.	$W_{MAN} = I_{MAN} \times IVA$ <p>The intensity of water use in the manufacturing industry is expressed as a function of GDP per capita and the composition of the manufacturing industry:</p> $\ln(I_{MAN}) = b_0 + b_1 \times \ln(GDP_{ca}) + b_2 \times \ln(R_{HL})$	WaterGAP2 global water use model equation SSP-RCP scenarios	China/Pearl river delta	Yao et al.,2017	
Commercial water demand	ICP: income per capita	$COMWAT = 0.006 * Population + 0.2 * PCI + 0.003$	Linear regression model	City of Addis Ababa/ Ethiopia	Kitessa et al.,2021	